

A SECURE NETWORK CODE BASED SERVER STORAGE SYSTEM WITH SECURE PROXY RE-ENCRYPTION

SHAHUL HAMEED A ¹, Dr. A. SHAJI GEORGE ²

Indian Institute of Integrated Science Technology and Research (IIISTR) India.

E-mail: ¹ashahul@yahoo.com; ²drashajigeorge@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A distributed storage framework, comprising of an assortment of capacity workers, gives long haul stockpiling administrations over the Internet. Putting away information in an outsider's cloud framework causes genuine worry over information classification. General encryption plans ensure information classification, yet additionally limit the usefulness of the capacity framework in light of the fact that a couple of activities are upheld over scrambled information. Developing a safe stockpiling framework that underpins different capacities is testing when the capacity framework is dispersed and has no focal power. We propose a limit intermediary re-encryption conspire and coordinate it with a decentralized deletion code with the end goal that a secure disseminated stockpiling framework is figured. The disseminated stockpiling framework not just backings secure and vigorous information stockpiling and recovery, yet additionally gives a client forward his information access the capacity workers to another client without recovering the information back. The fundamental specialized commitment is that the intermediary re-encryption plot upholds encoding tasks over scrambled messages just as sending tasks over encoded and scrambled messages. Our technique completely incorporates scrambling, encoding, and sending. We examine and propose reasonable boundaries for the quantity of duplicates of a message dispatched to capacity workers and the quantity of capacity workers questioned by a key worker. These boundaries permit more adaptable change between the quantity of capacity workers and strength.

Keywords: *Cloud storage, Framework, Re-encryption, Public key, private key, cloud computing.*

1.INTRODUCTION

As high-speed networks and ubiquitous Internet access become available in recent years, many services are provided on the Internet such that users can use them from anywhere at any time. For example, the email service is probably the most popular one. Cloud computing

is a concept that treats the resources on the Internet as a unified entity, a cloud. Users just use services without being concerned about how computation is done and storage is managed. In this paper, we focus on designing a cloud storage system for robustness, confidentiality, and functionality. A cloud storage system is considered as a largescale distributed storage system that consists of many independent storage servers. Data robustness is a major requirement for storage systems. There have been many proposals of storing data over storage servers [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. One way to provide data robustness is to replicate a message such that each storage server stores a copy of the message. It is very robust because the message can be retrieved as long as one storage server survives. Another way is to encode a message of k symbols into a codeword of n symbols by erasure coding. To store a message, each of its codeword symbols is stored in a different storage server. A storage server failure corresponds to a deletion blunder of the codeword image. However long the number of disappointment workers is under the resistance limit of the deletion code, the message can be recuperated from the codeword images put away in the accessible stockpiling workers by the interpreting cycle. This gives a trade off between the capacity size and the resistance limit of disappointment workers. A decentralized deletion code is an eradication code that autonomously registers each codeword image for a message. Accordingly, the encoding cycle for a message can be part into n equal undertakings of creating codeword images. A decentralized deletion code is appropriate for use in a dispersed stockpiling framework. After the message images are shipped off capacity workers, every capacity worker autonomously figures a codeword image for the got message images and stores it. This completes the encoding and putting away cycle. The recuperation measure is the equivalent.

Putting away information in an outsider's cloud framework causes genuine worry on information classification. To give solid classification for messages away workers, a client can scramble messages by a cryptographic technique prior to applying an eradication code strategy to encode and store messages. At the point when he needs to utilize a message, he needs to recover the codeword images from capacity workers, translate them, and at that point unscramble them by utilizing cryptographic keys. There are three issues in the above clear joining of encryption and encoding. To start with, the client needs to do most calculation and the correspondence traffic between the clientalso, capacity workers is high. Second, the client needs to oversee his cryptographic keys. In the event that the client's gadget of putting away the keys is lost or bargained, the security is broken. At last, other than information putting away and recovering, it is difficult for capacity workers to

straightforwardly uphold different capacities. For instance, capacity workers can't straightforwardly advance a client's messages to another. The proprietor of messages needs to recover, unravel, decode and afterward forward them to another client.

2.RELATED WORKS

We briefly review distributed storage systems, proxy reencryption schemes, and integrity checking mechanisms.

Distributed Storage Systems

At the early years, the Network-Attached Storage (NAS) [7] and the Network File System (NFS) [8] provide extrastorage devices over the network such that a user can access the storage devices via network connection. Afterward, many improvements on scalability, robustness, efficiency, and security were proposed [1], [2], [9].

A decentralized architecture for storage systems offers good scalability, because a storage server can join or leave without control of a central authority. To provide robustness against server failures, a simple method is to make replicas of each message and store them in different servers. However, this method is expensive as z replicas result in z times of expansion. One way to reduce the expansion rate is to use erasure codes to encode messages [10], [11], [12], [13], [5]. A message is encoded as a codeword, which is a vector of symbols, and each storage server stores a codeword symbol. A storage server failure is modeled as an erasure error of the stored codeword symbol. Random linear codes support distributed encoding, that is, each codeword symbol is independently computed. To store a message of k blocks, each storage server linearly combines the blocks with randomly chosen coefficients and stores the codeword symbol and coefficients. To retrieve the message, a user queries k storage servers for the stored codeword symbols and coefficients and solves the linear system. Dimakis et al. [13] considered the case that $n \geq ak$ for a fixed constant a . They showed that distributing each block of a message to v randomly chosen storage servers is enough to have a probability $1 - \frac{1}{k^p}$ of a successful data retrieval, where $v \geq \frac{b}{\ln k}$, $b > 5a$, and p is the order of the used group. The sparsity parameter $\frac{v}{\ln k}$ is the number of storage servers which a block is sent to. The larger v is, the communication cost is higher and the successful retrieval probability is higher. The system has a light data confidentiality because an attacker can compromise k storage servers to get the message.

Lin and Tzeng [6] addressed robustness and confidentiality issues by presenting a secure decentralized erasurecode for the networked storage system. In addition to storage servers, their system consists of key servers, which hold cryptographic key shares and work in a distributed way. In their system, stored messages are encrypted and then encoded. To retrieve a message, key servers query storage servers for the user. As long as the number of available key servers is over a threshold t , the message can be successfully retrieved with an overwhelming probability.

One of their results shows that when there are n storage servers with $n \geq \frac{1}{\epsilon} \log \frac{1}{\epsilon}$, the parameter v is $\log \frac{1}{\epsilon}$ with $\epsilon > 5\alpha$, and each key server queries 2 storage servers for each retrieval request, the probability of a successful retrieval is at least $1 - \epsilon$.

3. PROXY RE-ENCRYPTION SCHEMES

Intermediary re-encryption plans are proposed by Mambo and Okamoto [14] and Blaze et al. [15]. In an intermediary re-encryption plot, an intermediary worker can move a ciphertext under a public key PKA to another one under another public key PKB by utilizing the re-encryption key RKA $\rightarrow$ B. The worker doesn't have the foggiest idea about the plaintext during change. Ateniese et al. [16] proposed some intermediary re-encryption conspiracies and applied them to the sharing capacity of secure stockpiling frameworks. In their work, messages are first encoded by the proprietor and afterward put away in a capacity worker. At the point when a client needs to share his messages, he sends a re-encryption key to the capacity worker. The capacity worker re-scrambles the scrambled directives for the approved client. Hence, their framework has information secrecy and supports the information sending capacity. Our work further incorporates encryption, re-encryption, and encoding with the end goal that capacity heartiness is reinforced.

Type-based intermediary re-encryption plans proposed by Tang [17] give a superior granularity on the allowed right of a re-encryption key. A client can choose which sort of messages also, with whom he needs to partake in this sort of intermediary re-encryption plans. Key-private intermediary re-encryption plans are proposed by Ateniese et al. [18]. In a key-private intermediary re-encryption conspiracy, given a re-encryption key, an intermediary worker can't decide the personality of the beneficiary. This sort of intermediary re-encryption plans gives higher security ensure against intermediary workers. Albeit most intermediary re-

encryption plans use matching activities, there exist intermediary re-encryption plans without matching.

Fig. 1. A general system model of our work.

Integrity Checking Functionality

Another important functionality about cloud storage is the function of integrity checking. After a user stores data into the storage system, he no longer possesses the data at hand. The user may want to check whether the data are properly stored in storage servers. The concept of provable data possession [20], [21] and the notion of proof of storage [22], [23], [24] are proposed. Later, public auditability of stored data is addressed in [25]. Nevertheless all of them consider the messages in the cleartext form.

4. SCENARIO

We present the scenario of the storage system, the threat model that we consider for the confidentiality issue, and a discussion for a straightforward solution.

As appeared in Fig. 1, our framework model comprises of clients, n capacity workers SS_1 ; SS_2 ; ... ; SS_n , and m key workers KS_1 ; KS_2 ; ... ; KS_m . Capacity workers give stockpiling administrations and key workers give key administration administrations. They work autonomously. Our appropriated stockpiling framework comprises of four stages: framework arrangement, information stockpiling, information sending, and information recovery. These four stages are depicted as follows.

In the framework arrangement stage, the framework supervisor picks framework boundaries and distributes them. Every client A_n is doled out a public-mystery key pair $(PKA; SKA)$. Client A conveys his mystery key SKA to key workers with the end goal that each key worker KSi holds a key offer SKA_i . The key is imparted to an edge t .

In the information stockpiling stage, client A scrambles his message M what's more, dispatches it to capacity workers. A message M is deteriorated into k squares $m_1; m_2; \dots; m_k$ and has an identifier ID. Client A scrambles each square m_i into a ciphertext C_i and sends it to v haphazardly picked capacity workers. Upon getting cipher texts from a client, every capacity worker directly consolidates them with haphazardly picked coefficients into a codeword image and stores it. Note that a capacity worker may get not exactly k message squares and we expect that all stockpiling workers know the worth k ahead of time.

In the information sending stage, client A_n advances his encoded message with an identifier ID put away workers to client B such that B can decode the sent message by his mystery key. To do as such, A utilizes his mystery key SKA and B's public key PKB to process a re-encryption key $RKID_{A \rightarrow B}$ and afterward sends $RKID_{A \rightarrow B}$ to all stockpiling workers. Every capacity worker utilizes the re-encryption key to re-encode its codeword image for some other time recovery demands by B. The re-scrambled codeword image is the blend of ciphertexts under B's public key. All together to recognize re-scrambled codeword images from unblemished ones, we call them unique codeword images and re-encrypted code word images, individually.

In the information recovery stage, client A solicitations to recover a message from capacity workers. The message is either put away by him or sent to him. Client A sends a recovery demand to key workers. After accepting the recovery demand and executing an appropriate confirmation measure with client A, each key worker KSi demands u haphazardly picked capacity workers to get codeword images and does incomplete unscrambling on the gotten codeword images by utilizing the key offer SKA_i . At long last, client A consolidates the halfway unscrambled codeword images to acquire the first message M . Framework recuperating. At the point when a capacity worker fizzles, another one is added. The new stockpiling worker inquiries k accessible stockpiling workers, straightly consolidates the got codeword images as another one and stores it. The framework is then recuperated.

We consider information secrecy for both information stockpiling and information sending. In this danger model, an aggressor needs to break information secrecy of an objective client.

To do as such, the assailant conspires with all stockpiling workers, nontarget clients, furthermore, up to δt 1β key workers. The aggressor investigates put away messages away workers, the mystery keys of nontarget clients, and the shared keys put away in key workers. Note that the capacity workers store all re-encryption keys gave by clients. The aggressor may attempt to produce another re-encryption key from put away re-encryption keys. We officially model this assault by the standard picked plaintext attack1 of the intermediaryre-encryption plot in an edge rendition, as appeared in Fig. 2. The challenger C gives the framework boundaries. After the assailant A picks an objective client T , the challenger gives him δt 1β key portions of the mystery key SK_T of the objective client T to show δt 1β traded off key workers. At that point, the assailant can question mystery keys of different clients and all re-encryption keys aside from those from T to different clients. This models traded off non target clients and capacity workers. In the test stage, the assailant picks two messages M_0 and M_1 with the identifiers ID_0 and ID_1 , separately.

The challenger tosses an irregular coin b and encodes the message M_b with T 's public key PK_T . Subsequent to getting the ciphertext from the challenger, the assailant yields a touch b_0 for speculating b . In this game, the assailant wins if and just if $b_0 \neq b$. The benefit of the aggressor is characterized as $\epsilon = 2 \Pr[b_0 \neq b]$.

A distributed storage framework displayed in the above is secure if no probabilistic polynomial time aggressor dominates the match with a non negligible bit of leeway. A protected distributed storage framework suggests that an unapproved client or worker can't

Operation	Computation cost
Enc	$k \text{ Pairing} + k \text{ Exp}_1 + k \text{ Mult}_2$
Encode (for each storage server)	$k \text{ Exp}_1 + k \text{ Exp}_2$ $+ (k - 1) \text{ Mult}_1 + (k - 1) \text{ Mult}_2$
KeyRecover	$O(t^2) F_p$
ReKeyGen	1 Exp_1
ReEnc (for each storage server)	$1 \text{ Pairing} + 1 \text{ Mult}_2$
ShareDec (for t key servers)	$t \text{ Exp}_1$
Combine	$k \text{ Pairing} + t \text{ Mult}_1$ $+ (t - 1) \text{ Exp}_1 + O(t^2 + k^3) F_p$ $+ k^2 \text{ Exp}_2 + (k + 1)k \text{ Mult}_2$

- Pairing: a pairing computation of $\tilde{e}$.
- Exp_1 and Exp_2 : a modular exponentiation computation in $\mathbb{G}_1$ and $\mathbb{G}_2$, respectively.
- Mult_1 and Mult_2 : a modular multiplication computation in $\mathbb{G}_1$ and $\mathbb{G}_2$, respectively.
- F_p : an arithmetic operation in $GF(p)$.

Theorem 1.

Assume that there are k blocks of a message, n storage servers, and m key servers, where $n \geq k$, $m \geq t$, $c \geq 1$ and a is a constant with $a > 2$. For $v \geq k$ and $u \geq 2$ with $b > 5a$, the probability of a successful retrieval is at least $1 - \frac{1}{k^p}$.

Theorem 2.

Our cloud storage system described is secure under the threat model, if the decisional bilinear Diffie-Hellman assumption holds. In the information stockpiling stage, a client runs the Enc calculation and every capacity worker plays out the Encode calculation. In the Enc calculation, producing each i requires an Exp_1 , and producing each i requires an Exp_1 , a Blending, and a Mult_2 . Thus, for k squares of a message, the cost is $(k \text{ Pairing} + 2k \text{ Exp}_1 + k \text{ Mult}_2)$. For the Encode calculation, every capacity worker encodes k ciphertexts at most. The expense is $k \text{ Exp}_1 + k \text{ Mult}_1$ for figuring also, $k \text{ Exp}_2 + k \text{ Mult}_2$ for registering.

6.DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we consider a distributed storage framework comprises of capacity workers and key workers. We incorporate a recently LIN AND TZENG: A SECURE ERASURE CODE-BASED CLOUD STORAGE SYSTEM WITH SECURE DATA FORWARDING 1001 TABLE 1 The Computation Cost of Each Algorithm in Our Secure Cloud Storage System proposed limit intermediary re-encryption plot and eradication codes over types. The limit intermediary reencryption conspire underpins encoding, sending, and incomplete unscrambling activities in an appropriated way. To unscramble a message of k squares that are encoded and encoded to n codeword images, each key worker just has to halfway unscramble two codeword images in our framework.

By utilizing the edge intermediary re-encryption plot, we present a safe distributed storage framework that gives secure information stockpiling and secure information sending usefulness in a decentralized structure. Besides, every capacity worker freely performs encoding and re-encryption and each key worker autonomously performs halfway decoding.

Our capacity framework and some recently proposed content addressable record frameworks and capacity framework [27], [28], [29] are exceptionally viable. Our capacity workers go about as capacity hubs in a substance addressable capacity framework for putting away content addressable squares. Our key workers go about as access hubs for giving a front-end layer, for example, a customary record framework interface. Further investigation on nitty gritty collaborationis required.

REFERENCES:

- [1] J. Kubiawicz, D. Bindel, Y. Chen, P. Eaton, D. Geels, R. Gummadi, S. Rhea, H. Weatherspoon, W. Weimer, C. Wells, and B. Zhao, "Oceanstore: An Architecture for Global-Scale Persistent Storage," Proc. Ninth Int'l Conf. Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems (ASPLOS), pp. 190- 201, 2000.
- [2] P. Druschel and A. Rowstron, "PAST: A Large-Scale, Persistent Peer-to-Peer Storage Utility," Proc. Eighth Workshop Hot Topics in Operating System (HotOS VIII), pp. 75-80, 2001.
- [3] A. Adya, W.J. Bolosky, M. Castro, G. Cermak, R. Chaiken, J.R. Douceur, J. Howell, J.R. Lorch, M. Theimer, and R. Wattenhofer, "Farsite: Federated, Available, and Reliable Storage for an Incompletely Trusted Environment," Proc. Fifth Symp. Operating System Design and Implementation (OSDI), pp. 1-14, 2002.
- [4] A. Haeberlen, A. Mislove, and P. Druschel, "Glacier: Highly Durable, Decentralized Storage Despite Massive Correlated Failures," Proc. Second Symp. Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI), pp. 143-158, 2005.

- [5] Z. Wilcox-O’Hearn and B. Warner, “Tahoe: The Least-Authority Filesystem,” Proc. Fourth ACM Int’l Workshop Storage Security and Survivability (StorageSS), pp. 21-26, 2008.
- [6] H.-Y. Lin and W.-G. Tzeng, “A Secure Decentralized Erasure Code for Distributed Network Storage,” IEEE Trans. Parallel and Distributed Systems, vol. 21, no. 11, pp. 1586-1594, Nov. 2010.
- [7] D.R. Brownbridge, L.F. Marshall, and B. Randell, “The Newcastle Connection or Unixes of the World Unite!,” Software Practice and Experience, vol. 12, no. 12, pp. 1147-1162, 1982.
- [8] R. Sandberg, D. Goldberg, S. Kleiman, D. Walsh, and B. Lyon, “Design and Implementation of the Sun Network Filesystem,” Proc. USENIX Assoc. Conf., 1985.
- [9] M. Kallahalla, E. Riedel, R. Swaminathan, Q. Wang, and K. Fu, “Plutus: Scalable Secure File Sharing on Untrusted Storage,” Proc. Second USENIX Conf. File and Storage Technologies (FAST), pp. 29- 42, 2003.
- [10] S.C. Rhea, P.R. Eaton, D. Geels, H. Weatherspoon, B.Y. Zhao, and J. Kubiatowicz, “Pond: The Oceanstore Prototype,” Proc. Second USENIX Conf. File and Storage Technologies (FAST), pp. 1-14, 2003.
- [11] R. Bhagwan, K. Tati, Y.-C. Cheng, S. Savage, and G.M. Voelker, “Total Recall: System Support for Automated Availability Management,” Proc. First Symp. Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI), pp. 337-350, 2004.
- [12] A.G. Dimakis, V. Prabhakaran, and K. Ramchandran, “Ubiquitous Access to Distributed Data in Large-Scale Sensor Networks through Decentralized Erasure Codes,” Proc. Fourth Int’l Symp. Information Processing in Sensor Networks (IPSN), pp. 111- 117, 2005.
- [13] A.G. Dimakis, V. Prabhakaran, and K. Ramchandran, “Decentralized Erasure Codes for Distributed Networked Storage,” IEEE Trans. Information Theory, vol. 52, no. 6 pp. 2809-2816, June 2006.
- [14] M. Mambo and E. Okamoto, “Proxy Cryptosystems: Delegation of the Power to Decrypt Ciphertexts,” IEICE Trans. Fundamentals of Electronics, Comm. and Computer Sciences, vol. E80-A, no. 1, pp. 54- 63, 1997.
- [15] M. Blaze, G. Bleumer, and M. Strauss, “Divertible Protocols and Atomic Proxy Cryptography,” Proc. Int’l Conf. Theory and Application of Cryptographic Techniques (EUROCRYPT), pp. 127-144, 1998.
- [16] G. Ateniese, K. Fu, M. Green, and S. Hohenberger, “Improved Proxy Re-Encryption Schemes with Applications to Secure Distributed Storage,” ACM Trans. Information and System Security, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1-30, 2006.
- [17] Q. Tang, “Type-Based Proxy Re-Encryption and Its Construction,” Proc. Ninth Int’l Conf. Cryptology in India: Progress in Cryptology (INDOCRYPT), pp. 130-144, 2008.
- [18] G. Ateniese, K. Benson, and S. Hohenberger, “Key-Private Proxy Re-Encryption,” Proc. Topics in Cryptology (CT-RSA), pp. 279-294, 2009.
- [19] J. Shao and Z. Cao, “CCA-Secure Proxy Re-Encryption without Pairings,” Proc. 12th Int’l Conf. Practice and Theory in Public Key Cryptography (PKC), pp. 357-376, 2009.
- [20] G. Ateniese, R. Burns, R. Curtmola, J. Herring, L. Kissner, Z. Peterson, and D. Song, “Provable Data Possession at Untrusted Stores,” Proc. 14th ACM Conf. Computer and Comm. Security (CCS), pp. 598-609, 2007.

[21] G. Ateniese, R.D. Pietro, L.V. Mancini, and G. Tsudik, "Scalable and Efficient Provable Data Possession," Proc. Fourth Int'l Conf. Security and Privacy in Comm. Networks (SecureComm), pp. 1-10, 2008.